

IoT Gateway Virtualization for 5G mMTC Network Slicing

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Abstract—The advent of 5G is expected to facilitate the deployment and integration of IoT infrastructure, through the radio access network (RAN) support for scalable cellular coverage. This is foreseen to enable the integration of thin IoT devices into massive machine type communication (mMTC) services, typically realized within the scope of corresponding network slices. At the same time, the emergence of edge computing and supporting virtualization and programmability technologies, promises the convergence of the IoT platform and the telecommunication domains, allowing for the integration of IoT platform capabilities, such as IoT gateway (IoT-GW) functionality, within the operational scope of 5G network slices. In this paper, we take a close look at the role of IoT-GW functionality in the support of mMTC network slices, highlighting its importance in the definition of promising (IoT) infrastructure sharing models, extending up to the sharing of the IoT resources. We introduce a modular slicing architecture, which enables virtualization at the IoT GW level and mediated, coordinated communication with IoT devices. Based on this architecture and supporting orchestration mechanisms, we illustrate our proof of concept prototype based on open source components.

Keywords—Slicing, 5G, mMTC, IoT gateway

I. INTRODUCTION

Emerging 5G networking technologies are expected to foster the IoT vision of seamless integration between the real world of Things and the Information Technology domain, both for business e.g., Industry 4.0, and for everyday life scenarios e.g., smart cities. The expected support for massive machine type communications (mMTC), promises the simplification of IoT infrastructure deployment and operation, via scalable cellular coverage i.e., in the order of 1 million devices per Km² [1], offering low energy consumption/extended device lifetime e.g., reaching 15 years [1]. At the same time, the upcoming integration of compute and storage resources within the 5G infrastructure, including the network edge, is expected to support the convergence between the IoT platform and the telecommunication domains, allowing for the integration of IoT platform capabilities within the 5G network. Indeed, the emerging support for edge computing inherently gives ground to the functional integration of essential IoT Platform components [2] such as IoT Gateways, with the purpose of enabling local, low latency functionality, including data (pre-)processing for traffic reduction at the backhaul and core network.

5G networks are largely characterized by the support of network slicing. In general, network slicing aims at enabling the instantiation of logical networks, comprised of network functions, and resources to run these network functions, tailored to meet certain network characteristics required by the

Fig. 1: IoT Slicing Models

owner of the network slice [3]. Typically, network slicing is associated with the sharing of the underlying resources by individual *tenants*, as it builds on virtualization and programmability techniques to realize the co-existence of multiple logical networks on top of the same infrastructure. As such, associated technological approaches aim to support the resource and performance isolation of co-existing network slices, allowing tenants to securely share the same infrastructure.

In this context, it is of particular interest to take a close look at network slicing in the context of mMTC communications and the various modes of integration of IoT platforms within the virtualized 5G infrastructure, resulting to different slicing models (Fig. 1). To this end, we put particular emphasis on the role of IoT Gateways (IoT-GWs) considering them as important elements of the underlying shared infrastructure, opening up opportunities for the definition of new resource sharing models corresponding to different business relationships. We argue that IoT-GWs, as natural points of data aggregation and (pre-)processing, offer the opportunity to extend the scope of network slicing to the IoT device realm. IoT-GWs by inherently mediating access to the IoT device data (and configuration operations), can be employed to support the sharing of common IoT device data by multiple actors. This becomes

particularly interesting in certain application domains such as smart cities, where a common IoT device infrastructure can facilitate the emergence of different virtual IoT (vIoT) platform operators providing added value services. For instance, let us consider a toy example where a single IoT device infrastructure including air quality, temperature, traffic monitoring sensors can support both a traffic management service supported by the Municipality, and a third party service providing environmental friendly routes. Different IoT device deployment and ownership schemes can facilitate this sharing model, including telecommunication operators or single IoT Platform operators as the owners of the shared IoT infrastructure.

Given these insights, in this paper, we take a holistic view on the emerging opportunities for network slicing in the IoT domain, exploring the design space taking into account the important role of IoT-GW functionality. To this end, we first provide an overview of widely established and desired functional features of IoT-GWs so as to gain a better understanding of the implications of each sharing/network slicing model on the technological front (Section II). We then delve into the details of the models presenting the corresponding business models and discussing the implications on a technical level, including novel aspects on IoT-GW virtualization and corresponding management and orchestration (MANO) challenges (Section III). Focusing on the concept of IoT-GW virtualization, we further provide an architectural framework for the support of the corresponding mMTC network slicing model (Section 3). Taking a step further, we discuss system aspects and share experiences from our development activities building on the Linux Foundation EdgeXFoundry framework [4] and the Open Source MANO orchestration framework [5] in Section V.

II. IOT GATEWAY FUNCTIONALITY

IoT GW functionality commonly includes (i) data pre-processing and transformations, and (ii) events/alerts and embedded actuation logic. The realization of this functionality is typically considered at the edge of the network infrastructure, where local processing and decision making can support: (a) Low latency: low response times, enabling timely actuation, especially in mission critical cyber-physical systems (CPS), and (b) Scalability: opportunities for load reduction by enabling the aggregation and/or filtering of data prior to entering the transport domain and reaching centralized backend locations.

Fig. 2: IoT Platform stack.

Figure 2 depicts a generic reference architecture of an IoT GW, resulting from a review on existing open-source IoT

frameworks such as EdgeXFoundry, OpenHAB, DSA, OM2M, Fog05, KURA, Kapua, HONO, and IoTivity. The architecture aims to capture the main IoT GW capabilities and act as a reference framework for the subsequent description of IoT slicing primitives. It is mainly inspired by EdgexFoundry [4]—our selected framework for the system solution—and consists of multiple layers, the layers to the bottom being closer to the IoT devices and the layers to the top closer to the applications. *Device Communication*: this bottom layer is responsible for the direct communication of the IoT GW with the IoT devices. It translates messages to/from device-understandable protocols and communicates them to upper layers, formats data (device capabilities and measurements) for upstream delivery to upper platform layers and translates received commands downstream to device language.

Core Services: this layer acts as the reference point for upper layers, namely for i) collected data and command management from/to the device communication layer and ii) metadata management (device profiles, measurements datatypes, etc.) as exposed by the Device Communication layer.

Information Services: this layer deals with advanced data processing (Data Analytics) over the collected data, Data Persistence and Events and Rule Management, triggered by rules explicitly defined by registered and authorized users.

Front End Services: the upmost layer of an IoT GW, offers a GUI, manages users registration to different services and distributes data to northbound applications.

Service Registry Configuration: vertical to all above-mentioned layers this entity is responsible for component-level status and health checks and as a reference point for application-wide configurations.

In addition, there is a vertical layer for *Security and Safety*, as well as a layer for *Operation Management*, providing a management view to the platform operator.

III. IOT SLICING MODELS

Exploring the integration of network slicing with mMTC communications, we identify below the distinct responsibilities which can be undertaken by different or by the same actors, depending on the level of exposure of infrastructure and IoT platform services. Actors in this ecosystem can include Telecom Operators, IoT Platform operators, civilians and potentially any entity able to register/connect their infrastructural/management resources via open, standardized APIs.

IoT device provisioning: offering & registration of physical infrastructure, i.e., smart devices and edge equipment to appropriate slice(s).

Infrastructure Operation & Management: management of the physical & virtual IoT infrastructure, including operation and maintenance of physical/virtual resources.

Virtualization & Slicing: interaction with IoT resources, virtualization and mediated provisioning, definition and enforcement/control of the interaction boundaries and QoS.

IoT Slice ownership: mediated ownership of virtualized underlying devices and platforms for the development & deployment of IoT services, including configuration and management primitives within the slice limits.

In what follows, we describe notable slicing models derived by varying degrees of integration of the above-mentioned responsibilities in the formed ecosystem.

A. Baseline mMTC Slicing Model

As a baseline mMTC network slicing approach, we consider the ability of the 5G network to dedicate wireless and wired network, as well as compute and storage resources, to the communication needs of individual sets of IoT devices (UEs) owned, deployed and operated by prospective IoT platform operators. Prospective IoT platform operators, deploy their IoT devices relying on the establishment of mIoT network slices for the support of the corresponding communication needs. As a result, IoT devices are presented with network slice instances to select from, so as to be integrated in the 5G facility control and data plane e.g., device authentication, data forwarding.

Network resources are allocated by each slice for the transmission and delivery of IoT data, either from or to the IoT devices (e.g., in case of actuators). Compute and storage resources are also allocated for the support of 5G Core functions required for this integration, covering IoT Gateway (GW) functionality (if not realized as a dedicated PNF). The described model is depicted in Fig. 1a. The exclusivity of resources per slice simplifies management, as well as the enactment of actuation logic and allows tenants to seamlessly onboard, manage and configure their own IoT devices.

Following this model in our toy example from the smart city domain, each tenant—in this case the Municipality and a (private) Service Provider—is provided with a slice, which has its own dedicated IoT Infrastructural resources (smart devices, networking, control/management functionality). The transmission and delivery of data from the smart devices within a slice are end-to-end isolated and independent from the existence of other slices and the control/management functionality extends uninterrupted from the tenants all the way down to the IoT devices.

B. Extended mMTC Slicing Model

Building on the baseline IoT Slicing approach, an extended IoT Slicing model is further targeted, where emphasis is put on the sharing of existing IoT resources. Namely, the objective is to allow the sharing of the same IoT devices by different Slice owners, the former being owned and deployed by IoT infrastructure stakeholders, as illustrated in Fig. 1b. Example stakeholders include network infrastructure operators that extend their network infrastructure with IoT devices (sensors, actuators) or even IoT Platform operators operating mIoT network slices.

While the support of IoT device virtualization appears as the straightforward approach, the intended scale of mIoT slices (i.e., 1 M devices / Km²) presents significant scalability and complexity concerns, when considering the creation of one virtual IoT device instance per instantiated mIoT slice. Bypassing these concerns, in the extended IoT sharing model, IoT devices become a shared commodity on the IoT GW level, where mediation is provided for the coordinated communication with devices. This virtualization at the GW level allows for the separation of concerns between different stakeholders and thus, the streamlining of IoT services on-boarding and deployment.

To this end, this Slicing model is compatible with a PaaS sharing approach, with virtualized IoT GW instances (vIoT-GW) dedicated to the support of the corresponding IoT slices.

vIoT-GWs can be realized as software units (e.g., VNFs), each delivered to a single slice of the extended mIoT slice type.

A north-bound interface (NBI) of such virtualized instance can provide application support, in an IoT Slicing-agnostic manner i.e., facilitating data delivery (e.g., MQTT based); exposure of IoT devices, their capabilities and configuration interfaces; Rule Management; User Management, as well as traditional FCAPS tasks. A south-bound interface (SBI) handles the interconnection with an underlying IoT GW (Host IoT-GW), common for different slices and operated by the Telecom Operator. The Host IoT-GW is responsible for the management of the devices in the field, supporting the physical interface to the IoT infrastructure in an IoT Slicing-orthogonal manner. At the same time it realizes the IoT GW virtualization primitives by mediating access of IoT GW VNFs to the underlying infrastructure e.g., delivering sub-streams of data and realizing conflict resolution for actuators. This corresponds to the realization of a Virtualized IoT Infrastructure Management (VIoTIM) system, in an analogy to VIM for compute and storage resources, however bearing a PaaS flavor.

Hence, vIoT-GWs are responsible for exposing virtual views of the IoT device data, meta-data and control command interfaces within the corresponding slices, without incorporating any IoT device (UE) control plane functionality. Essentially, this corresponds to the virtualization of the Host IoT-G, operated by the infrastructure provider. As shown in Fig. 1b, the extended mMTC slice boundaries are located at the Edge of the network, where the virtualization of the Host IoT-GW takes place.

In spite of management overhead, the main benefit of unified mediation is the efficient reuse of existing IoT infrastructure (IoT devices, gateways, southbound mechanisms/configurations, management), lowering CAPEX/OPEX costs and removing entry barriers for IoT application owners. In addition, it allows the “Plug & Play” deployment of applications built for legacy IoT systems, since slice owners are presented with a virtualization-agnostic view of the underlying hardware, obsoleting the use of wrapper layers and glue code for interoperability.

In our toy example, according to this model, IoT Infrastructural resources can be shared between isolated tenants—the Municipality and the Service Provider—who are each provided with a sandboxed environment (i.e., slice). In this environment, tenants are each presented with a private view over sensors for air quality, temperature, traffic monitoring etc., and hence, they can interact with IoT resources and roll out their own smart city applications. On the other site the MNO monetizes the deployed IoT infrastructure.

C. Hybrid models

Considering variations of the above-described models, we can identify combinatory models constructed by allowing different degrees of unified mediation and management over underlying IoT infrastructure—introduced in the extended model—and resources exclusivity per slice—described in the baseline model. As an example, the extended model is compatible with the provisioning of dedicated IoT resources per slice, however with the management, control and data planes actually passing through the shared Host IoT-GW—which in

this case should be responsible for guaranteeing the (virtual) isolation.

Besides, the two extreme models, as well as their variations can physically coexist, with the infrastructure operator adopting versatile composition mechanisms to support the symbiosis of different slicing schemes.

IV. EXTENDED MMTC SLICING ARCHITECTURE

In order to realize the extended mMTC slice model, as sketched above, we split the functional primitives of the IoT GW reference architecture in two parts, with the purpose of deriving the functional boundaries between the network slice components, as realized by the vIoT-GW, and the operational control elements of the infrastructure owner. A single Host GW instance (e.g. a PNF) is available at the infrastructure operator side, effectively handling the virtualization of the IoT resources and their exposure to network slices. A single Guest IoT-GW instance is realized per instantiated network slice .

Fig. 3: Extended mMTC Slicing Architecture.

On the Host IoT-GW side, we preserve the Device Communication primitives and further introduce a Hypervisor layer, the Core Services Hypervisor. This component is responsible for mediating the communication between the Host GW and various Guest GWs, as illustrated in Figure 3. The hypervisor is responsible for the delivery of readings from and capabilities of the same devices to multiple isolated slices and for the resolution and imposition of actuation and control from multiple isolated slices, to the same devices (where applicable). It achieves these isolated interactions by mediating the bi-directional communication between the device services of the Host IoT-GW and the core services of each slice, namely: (i) upstream communication: data formatting (e.g., from one protocol to another) and capabilities advertisement towards core services, (ii) downstream communication: command translation towards devices.

The upstream mediation functionality of the hypervisor regards the dissemination (forwarding) of data sent from the Host IoT-GW to each slice about measurements and metadata, respectively via the Data Collection Mediator and the Device Metadata Mediator, interfacing with the Guest IoT-GW of network slices. Before delivering data to the various slices for consumption, the Mediators first check whether data can be simply duplicated and forked towards two or more recipients i.e., if data characteristics (e.g., frequency, accuracy) are the

same (or fall within acceptable limits for all slices). If that is not the case, then data becomes subject to the appropriate filtering/post-processing/aggregation.

The downstream mediation functionality of the Hypervisor, which is implemented by the Command Management Mediator, regards control scenarios, when slices request control actions over the same IoT devices. Actions are checked and if they are non-conflicting, they are propagated all the way down to the appropriate IoT device. In case of conflicts, resolution logic is enacted e.g., through the enforcement of predefined resolution policies . The mediation functionality is also responsible for the isolation of the different slices. This is first addressed via networking isolation, with one distinct subnet being mapped to each slice and the Host IoT-GW connecting via different interfaces to each subnet. Traffic policing mechanisms may also ensure compliance to the agreed SLAs between the operator and the slice owners. Moreover, each slice is deployed on its own isolated environment (i.e., Guest IoT-GW VM), with its own reserved computing/networking/storage resources (see also Section 5). At the same time, authentication and authorization mechanisms provide access control over the communication between the Host and Guest IoT-GWs regarding accessible devices, allowed readings rate, accepted commands etc.

The Core Services Hypervisor is controlled by the Hypervisor Controller, a component inside the Operation Management Layer of the Host IoT-GW, which is responsible for the communication with the Operator and the translation of instructions to slicing behaviour. The Hypervisor Controller is the management interface to the Operator for Host IoT-GW hypervisor services, receiving instructions in a declarative fashion (e.g., slice instantiation, IoT application level QoS, commands exclusivity on device for defined timeslot, prioritization in cases of conflict), translating them to control commands and enforcing them to the Core Services Hypervisor. Thus, it enforces and maintains slice management information and it constantly monitors the health of device services and the QoS satisfaction per slice, by receiving metrics/KPIs from Core Services Mediator and from the Host GW Operating System. Furthermore, it performs accounting through slicing-service-related logging and it reports to the Operator as prompted. An additional functionality of the Hypervisor Controller is the cross-hypervisor (East-West) communication, state transfer and consensus in scale-out scenarios, i.e., in cases when the devices services instance managing a set of IoT devices needs to horizontally scale, with new instances managing complementary and disjoint subsets of the original set of devices.

The Host GW architecture also includes its own vertical IoT Platform layers. Host GW Service Registry Configuration is responsible for service discovery, status/health check on a component level and application-wide configurations. It includes a Key-Value store for maintaining configuration parameters and it is used to also back other Host GW services (e.g., auth credentials, slices information, monitoring and accounting information, links to script files locations). Security and Safety on a Host GW level refers aspects of the GW and its interactions with the Operator and IoT devices. Finally, Operation Management is the MANO agent on the Host GW, providing a global view of all devices being controlled.

Fig. 4: Extended mMTC Slicing Prototype.

A. Slicing Orchestration

Our architecture has a modular design with clear-cut interfacing, to support easy management and orchestration of the lifecycle and configuration of slices. To showcase this capability, we present in this subsection the orchestration steps towards the instantiation of a new slice, in context of the NFV MANO architectural framework [1]. This stage assumes that a Host GW instance is already in an operational state, managing a set of IoT devices and exposing through the Operation Management all relevant MANO interfaces.

Step 1: Infrastructure Operator requests the creation of a new slice through the OSS/BSS, with specific characteristics, e.g., the IoT devices to be linked to the slice; QoS of networking, compute and storage resources to be allocated; security and isolation properties of the slice.

Step 2: Request is propagated to NFVO, who orders the instantiation of a (predefined) NSD that models the slice to be created. The NSD includes a VNFD, the VDU of which describes the VM image to be used as the Guest GW and the flavor (CPU, memory, storage) of the launched instance, dictated by the QoS characteristics of the previous step.

Step 3: The VIM instantiates the corresponding VM and applies networking configuration, ensuring Guest GW VM connectivity with the Host GW instance, exposure of Guest GW NBI interface to the appropriate network and potentially networking constrains (e.g., bandwidth, delay).

Steps 4 & 5: NFVO is requested by OSS/BSS to apply day-2 configurations first to the Host GW VNFI and then to the Guest GW VNFI. Relevant configuration primitives (parameterized accordingly, e.g., with IPs, MQTT keys) are activated and the VNFM instructs the VNFIs through their Operation & Management interfaces to configure the data plane from the Host GW to the Core Services of the new slice.

Upon completion of Steps 4 & 5, the Infrastructure Operator receives confirmation by the OSS/BSS component that the new slice is ready to be delivered to a tenant.

V. PROTOTYPE IMPLEMENTATION

Figure 4 depicts our Proof of Concept implementation of the extended mMTC slicing Architecture on our local testbed. To this end, we have employed a bare-metal server, running VMware ESXi, with a WiFi access point (TP-Link) directly connected to the server, providing wireless connectivity to IoT devices. Three VMs—all running Ubuntu 16.04—have been launched and configured to support the end-to-end slicing orchestration: an OSM instance (2 CPU cores, 8G RAM, 100G HD) running Open Source MANO[5] Release 5, an OpenStack

(OS) Controller Node (4 CPU cores, 4G RAM, 40G HD) and an OS Compute Node (4 CPU cores, 16G RAM, 40G HD). Connectivity has been configured between OSM, the OS nodes and the WiFi access point interface, using Open vSwitch bridging.

Using the proper artifacts (NSDs and VNFDs) onboarded on OSM, we have successfully tested the orchestration of the lifecycle management of both Host GW and Guest GW instances, running as OS VMs inside the Openstack Compute Node (i.e., nested virtualization). For the Host GW VM, we have extended the bottom layer components of EdgeX Foundry [4], i.e., Device Services, with our custom implementation of Core Services Hypervisor and with a running Rabbit MQ message brokerage service, for MQTT-based data delivery to different slices. For the Guest GW VMs we use the EdgeX Foundry services as-is, with slight extension of the core services and the addition of our custom Operation Management component, for subscription to data delivery from Host GW.

We follow a micro-services architecture where all components/services, both within Host GW and Guest GWs are realized as Docker containers, communicating through overlay networks. We use OS Neutron Networking for the connectivity between the IoT sensors, the Host GW and the Guest GW, for isolation between different slices and for NBI access to slices.

VI. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we have presented our work on mMTC slicing, adopting a converged view over network slicing and IoT platforms. To this end, we have visited different modes of integration of IoT GW functionality with the virtualized 5G infrastructure and we have explored the different aspects and roles in the derived ecosystems. Focusing on resource efficiency and building on virtualization techniques, we have presented a novel architecture and orchestration mechanisms for the support of slicing, while enabling IoT resources shareability. Our proof of concept implementation shows the feasibility and agility of our approach and as future work, we plan to extend our prototype and migrate it to a large-scale testbed for conducting relevant KPI measurements.

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